

NEOLOGISMS IN MODERN MEDICAL ENGLISH

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ABSTRACT

Medicine as a science is full of terms - words and phrases denoting scientific concepts, which reflect the essential properties and characteristics of the object. Over the years, medicine has evolved. This can be seen in the analysis of medical terminology. With the development of medicine, terminology also developed, and many neologisms appeared.

Modern medical terminology is a collective concept, which includes many words and stable phrases that make up the terminological base of several biomedical disciplines. This is a naturally formed term system that has a centuries-old tradition. Research and study of the problems of medical terminology are extremely important and relevant since terminology is the main source of enriching the lexical composition of all modern languages. Is terminology an important part of every language that is considered a universal means of storing, transmitting, and processing information?

As one of the special branches of the so-called functional styles that serve different fields of science, the sublanguage of medicine differs from other professional sublanguages in its cognitive parameters, covering a huge complex of concepts combined into one capacious concept -

health protection. Through the content plan, the specificity of the professional sublanguage of medicine is reflected in the choice of terminological neologisms from all the linguistic means available in the language. A necessary condition for obtaining information and professional communication in a foreign language is the mastery of the terminological fund of the relevant specialty and professionally-oriented vocabulary that is directly related to it.

The nature of neologisms is heterogeneous. Based on this, neologisms are divided into lexical and stylistic.

Stylistic neologisms are words or new meanings of old words that denote already existing concepts and objects.

For example, heart failure: current concepts and management - heart failure: modern concepts and treatment.

Lexical neologisms, most of which are terms or nomenclatural words, are new or old words to denote new objects, phenomena, and concepts.

For example, pilot study – experimental study; red hypertension - benign (arterial) hypertension; rodent cancer – basal cell carcinoma, basal cell carcinoma, basal cell epithelioma; opportunistic pneumonia – pneumonia caused by opportunistic pathogens.

Neoplasms of medical terms are mainly formed by traditional methods: word composition; the method of telescoping, affixation; abbreviations. [3, 5-41]

According to the method of education, the studied medical neologisms can be classified as: affixal, the basis of which contains the root and affixes: para medicalization (the tendency to give preference to alternative methods of treatment), hospitalist (a physician practicing only in a hospital), superinfecter (a person who is a carrier of an infectious disease and deliberately spreads it); compound words containing at least two root morphemes: andropause ("menopausal period" in a man's life), photomedicine (a field of medicine that studies the use of light for the prevention and treatment of diseases) and compound words formed by composing two or more bases, one of which is formed by derivation: photo rejuvenation (a method of skin treatment using a light source or other thermal or chemical means to eliminate wrinkles caused by photoaging), neuropreservation (cryopreservation of the brain), psych ergonomics (study of factors of psychological balance of the human condition); abbreviations: SARS (severe acute respiratory syndrome – an acute infectious disease, such as pneumonia);

telescopisms: globesity (worldwide epidemic obesity), virtopsy (virtual autopsy performed using computer technology); the phrase: robotic check-ups (computer medical examination), phage therapy (the use of bacteriophage viruses to destroy bacteria that are pathogens of the disease), pharmafood (genetically modified foods with pharmacological components to reduce cholesterol, etc. genetic enhancement (genetic improvement). [1, 215]

How neologisms are formed:

1. Prefixes and suffixes are used to create neologisms. To indicate an excess or lack of something, the prefixes "over" and "under" are used, for example, overaction – hyperfunction; overdose – excessive dose, overabundance; over-breathing – hyperventilation, hyperpnea; underweight – weight loss; undernourishment – exhaustion, hypotrophy.

The suffix –er is used to form a new word with the meaning of a person producing an action, or a device, device, device: sleeper – a person who sleeps, over-sleeper – a person who sleeps more than required; downer - a depressant substance, pain-killer -analgesic, non-smoker / total abstainer - someone who does not smoke and completely abstains from smoking.

2. The role of each productive affix is more important than the role of a separate lexical neologism since each word-forming morpheme gives life to many lexical neologisms, which expands the possibilities of word-formation. So, a lot of neologisms in the field of medicine relating to the recently popular plastic surgery (surgiholic - a man with a mania to change his body beyond recognition with the help of plastic surgery), tummy tuck (liposuction), nose job (rhinoplasty). Recently, a new

procedure has appeared, proposed by dermatologists, tear-through fillers to make the eyes look fresh.

There are new language nominations for the designation of the impact of telecommunication technologies on the healthcare sector, for the designation of the organizational restructuring of the healthcare sector and the proposed institutions, for the designation of financial instruments (insurance, additional medical services, etc.) used in the field of medicine and healthcare, for the designation of ethical issues of modern medicine. The advent of computers and mobile phones has led to the emergence of new syndromes, for example, Carpal Tunnel Syndrome – a syndrome caused by repeated movements of the joints, especially the wrist, which can lead to numerous musculoskeletal problems; Computer Vision Syndrome - a degenerative eye problem that can lead to a significant decrease in vision (myopia), blurred vision, universal eye fatigue, and even glaucoma. New diseases and symptoms have also appeared: Cell Phone Rash – the symptoms of this allergy include a red rash and itching in areas where parts of a mobile phone containing nickel affecting the face may also damage the fingertips if you constantly touch the keys containing nickel; Cell Phone Addiction – dependence on a mobile phone, constant use and checking messages, often users get annoyed when they need to turn off the phone.

3. Conversion or change of the syntactic function of a word is a method of word formation, according to which another part of speech is formed from one part without any changes in the external form of the word. In this way, the noun becomes a verb or an adjective; the verb takes over the

functions of the noun, etc. For example, they cure him. – They treat him. How does the organism function? – How does this organism work?

4. Neologisms are often formed by shortening words by abbreviation. For example, TB – tuberculosis – tuberculosis, AIDS - Acquired immune deficiency syndrome - AIDS, acquired immunodeficiency syndrome; Tray (electromagnetic radiation with terahertz frequency); DNA fingerprint (DNA structure analysis), IT-rage (pathological anger directed at computer technology).

5. Sometimes neologisms are formed by analogy with existing words.

For example, normotensives – normotonic, hypertensives – hypertension, and hypotensive – hypotonic.

6. When translating complex words-neologisms, a method of rearranging components is used. For example, immune reconstitution – the restoration of the immune reactivity of the body, immunosuppression – suppression of immunity.

7. Most often neologisms are formed by adding a participle or adjective to another noun.

For example: histologically documented reference group – an observed group with histology, day-case laparoscopy – laparoscopy, drug-related adverse events – adverse reactions associated with taking medications.

8. An effective way to create medical neologisms is affixation – attaching prefixes and suffixes to roots or bases. Affixal medical neologisms are formed using morphemes available in the language system. For example, andrologist (a doctor dealing with men's health problems); rawism (raw food), surgical (a surgeon

working exclusively in a hospital); on-call-ologist (a doctor who often works on-call); intensivist (an emergency department doctor); thriver (an HIV-infected patient without any symptoms of the disease); wobblers (a patient with an affected vestibular system); prehypertension (slightly higher than normal blood pressure, which without treatment can lead to hypertension), over-prescription (prescribing excessive amounts of medications).

9. It should be noted that a significant number of medical neologisms are constructed with the help of affixed-word-forming elements undergoing the formation stage. In the studied sample, the most productive affixes are the prefixes bio-, cyber-, super-, cryo-, nano-, and the suffixes -mania, phobia. For example, bio-computer (a biocomputer is a device for computing at the DNA level), bioinformatics (bioinformatics is a science that processes data related to the decoding of the human genome), biomanufacturing (production of biopharmaceuticals using genetic engineering), biobank (biobank – storage of biomaterials for researching the problem of dependence of human diseases on the peculiarities of the genetic composition of people), cyberchondriac (a person composing diseases for himself), superbug (artificially produced virus), supertaster (a person with extremely developed taste receptors), cryopreservation (cryopreservation – low-temperature preservation of living biological with the possible restoration of their biological functions after defrosting).

10. A characteristic way of forming neologisms in the sub-dialect of medicine is telescoping - the fusion of two truncated bases of words, or the combination of a full

base with a truncated one, as a result of which a new word corresponding to the words in its warehouse is formed. A productive model for the formation of telescopes is $ab + cd = ad$, for example, pharmer (pharmacy + farmer) – a person engaged in obtaining medically active substances using biotechnologies; cosmeceuticals (cosmetic + pharmaceuticals) – drugs that combine medicinal properties with cosmetic; surgiholic (surgery + alcoholic) – a person who constantly resorts to plastic surgery; diabetes (diabetes + obesity) – diabetes caused by overweight. Another productive model is $ab + cd = and$. For example, psychache (psychological + ache) – extremely strong psychological pain, reprogenetics (reproductive + genetics) – the use of genetic technologies to change and control human reproductive function, obesogenic (obese + genic).

11. The terms containing the abbreviation of the initial and final elements of the original word are identified: man flu (flu ← influenza) (severe cold, which men mistakenly consider flu), bird flu (bird flu). When translating neologisms, the transliteration method is used. Therefore, transliteration is not only a special but also a common way of forming new words in medicine. The most common methods are descriptive translation, translation by analogy, rearrangement of components, and others.

For the research and storage of genetic and biological information, special institutions were created – banks, for example, cell bank (a bank of cells, a place of preservation of cells taken from human embryos), cord blood bank (storage of cord blood rich in stem cells), gene bank, biobank (storage of biomaterials for research).

Nevertheless, the number of special medical terms is increasing, many new scientific concepts and terms are appearing, and many old ones are changing or disappearing altogether. Therefore, it is sufficient to define the boundaries of its areas, sections, and subsections without using basic resources, such as English-language medical literature, since most of the medical information is published in English.

The appearance of neologisms is initially stimulated by cognitive-speech pragmatics since the emergence of a new word is intended to express the communicative-pragmatic intentions of communicants.

In the absence of the right word in the language system, one has to turn to the services of linguosemiosis or use the lexemes available in the language, which are forced to develop a new one necessary to express a new meaning. For example, the disease AIDS (acquired immunodeficiency syndrome), which was first associated with a "global health crisis", was previously described by the terms "sexual liberation", "sexual choice", and "sexual revolution". Then the terms "Kaposi's sarcoma", and "immunodeficiency" appeared, which determined the first symptoms of the disease. As you know, the immune system is designed to protect a living organism from the penetration of parasites into it. A violation of the defense system is called an immune deficiency or insufficiency. That's why the abbreviation SPIN is sometimes used instead of the term 'AIDS'. HIV infection later acquired the name 'acquired immune deficiency syndrome' (AIDS) "acquired immunodeficiency syndrome" (AIDS). An analysis of the literature on AIDS showed that at first doctors used the term "acquired immunodeficiency" in their

speech. This term turned out to be inaccurate.

Thus, the analysis of the neologisms of the speech of medicine found that the new medical terminology is most characterized by multi-lexeme terms, among which two-component term-word combinations predominate.

We can also analyze the term "sugar disease", which functioned at the beginning of the XX century and was associated with the presence of sugar in the blood. Soon, the term "diabetes" was borrowed from the Latin language, which turned out to be more accurate and more common in the speech of physicians.

Euphemism is a word or descriptive expression that is neutral in meaning and emotional "load", usually used in texts to replace other words and expressions that are considered indecent or inappropriate.

Groups of euphemisms:

- ☒ euphemisms that facilitate age-related infringement
- ☒ euphemisms that facilitate property infringement
- ☒ euphemisms that exclude discrimination against people with physical and mental disabilities
- ☒ euphemisms that mitigate racial and ethnic discrimination

The use of euphemisms in everyday medical practice helps to ensure compliance with the basic principle of communication (politeness) and is also an unspoken speech etiquette, a kind of professional rule. Fortunately for a medical translator, euphemisms are used as actors in the modern language of almost all countries as in Russian – and for the same purpose: to reduce the stress level of patients and their relatives.

In medicine, they try to replace the word "death" with euphemisms. So, for example, the verb to die is replaced by to deceive or to pass away, as well as to go West, to depart, to breathe one's last, to join the silent / the majority, to be no more, to lose one's life, to expire, to go behind the eternal cloud, to go to eternal heaven, to pay one's debt to nature, to go to the kingdom, to sleep the sleep that knows no waking, to go the way of all flesh. One can use idioms like to kick the bucket, to count daises, to pop one's clogs, to give up the ghost, to kick-off, to check out, to take a ride, to hop the twig (to give an oak, discard skates, play in a box), but they need to know the measure in these rude-joking expressions.

Groups of euphemisms that distract from the negative phenomena of reality:

☐ euphemisms for covering aggressive social actions (crime, drug addiction, aggressive politics): involvement - aggression; conflict - war; device - bomb; limited air strike/air support - bombing; training bases - military bases;

☐ euphemisms associated with negative consequences in the socio-economic sphere: reserve of the labor force - unemployment; culturally different children - slum children; downsizing, rightsizing - dismissal.

It is worth noting that the principal feature of euphemisms in medicine is their high versatility: the use of softening words performs several functions at once, they are focused on the patient and his relatives, therefore diminutiveness, low quality, and emphasized politeness are very often used. In medicine, it is almost impossible to avoid using euphemisms. And these euphemisms must be taken into account when performing a medical translation.

When translating texts with neologisms, a chain of difficulties arises. The first problem is understanding the meaning of a new word. Practically, the translation of a neologism is carried out in stages, depending on which type of words this neologism belongs to. The absence of a new word in the English-Russian or English-English explanatory dictionary does not mean its absence on the global Internet. The section "New Words" or "Slang" may well contain the necessary information. At the same time, it is recommended to use dictionaries of the latest editions or constantly updated modern online dictionaries. Neologisms are interesting for their impermanence; they disappear as quickly as they appear. Nevertheless, neologism should be perceived as a normal linguistic phenomenon, translators must necessarily contribute to the development of a new vocabulary and the absence of a word in the dictionary cannot serve as an obstacle to its translation.

The future goal is to develop special professionally directed dictionaries that would regulate language norms for representatives of specific professions: teachers, doctors, lawyers, etc. Euphemistic neologisms are an integral part of the lexical composition of any language.

In conclusion, I would like to say that English, like other languages, is constantly changing and evolving. Vocabulary, as the most mobile component of the language, reacts most subtly to all modifications in the social, cultural, and other spheres of life of the communicative collective. As a result of brain activity, a person understands the meanings of new terms and realizes the transformation of the meanings of existing ones. The desire for the rational adaptation of the meanings available in the linguistic

understanding, creating a new logical space, is extremely intense. The recent word enjoys a hugely influential force, forms a person's ability to fulfill the previously comprehended realities of his spiritual and practical activity, and stimulates his further cognitive interest. The new term conveys the nature of a person's mental activity in the field of medicine.

The new formations of the English language in the field of medicine and healthcare make a significant contribution to the enrichment of the vocabulary of the modern English language. The emergence of information

technologies, the emergence of new diseases, syndromes, symptoms, and methods of their treatment affect the emergence of new lexical categories for the exchange of medical information in the field of healthcare. Therefore, modern neology has several tasks that require urgent solutions, namely: the systematization of terminology; establishment of features of the conventionalization of new vocabulary in the conditions of the present; expansion of multi-aspect linguistic research on the latest language and speech material.

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